

FABRIC Experimenters Workshop Report Highlights
April 8-9, 2021

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Executive Summary

The FABRIC Experimenters Workshop virtually brought together over 191 active participants from around the globe to see demonstrations of the initial key modules that comprise the FABRIC testbed's Minimum Viable Product (MVP) as well as an early look into the Measurement Framework (MF). Participants were encouraged to provide real time feedback on the software. A combination of FABRIC team updates, science design driver updates, related project (CC* and FAB) updates, breakout sessions, experimenters whiteboard sessions, and an open mic ensured a rich dialog between the experimenters, other testbed conveners, partners hosting FABRIC infrastructure, and the FABRIC team. Despite the virtual format, participants were actively engaged.

Participation

The FABRIC team had an open registration for this two-day workshop, attracting 214 registrations. 191 attended on April 8th and a similar number attended on April 9th. An estimated 87 institutions across 9 countries were represented at the workshop, including: Belgium, Brazil, France, Ireland, Japan, the Netherlands, South Africa, United Kingdom, United States. FABRIC's [7 student interns](#) also attended.

FABRIC switched from Zoom to the Airmeet platform, which encourages participant interaction by design; participants could go to a virtual coffee room (the "lobby") and mingle, as well as be brought "on stage". Participants interacted with the speakers by asking questions via Airmeet chat, Q&A, and raising their hand to speak; the participants interacted with each other and the FABRIC team via Airmeet sessions, Airmeet lobby, and a FABRIC community Slack channel. The dialog was highly interactive.

Open Mic: Participant Feedback

A few highlights from participant feedback:

- People liked the use of Jupyter notebooks as the experimenter interface to FABRIC.
- Obtaining near-real time measurement data was discussed.
- A few people asked about providing access to (edge) data in a privacy preserving manner.
- Several questions arose on how to bring external data onto FABRIC.
- On the issue of carrying out experiments involving testing a system's resilience to faults (nodes, links, one, several), can fault injection be done "in band" (as part of a workload) or through API where we can do this programmatically?

Participant Talk Highlights

Next Generation Internet

Scott Shenker [gave a talk](#) on his vision for the “Extensible Internet” which creates layers on top of the current IP stack. The team will work with Scott to see if his idea can possibly be fit into Beta testing.

Science Design Drivers Spotlight

- Russ Clark described [his IoT experiment](#) being conducted in cooperation with the City of Savannah, Georgia.
- Alex Afanasiev, [Susmit Shannigrahi](#), and Alex Feltus described their NDN experiment.
- Paul Barford, who is working on capacity-building for FABRIC measurement capabilities, including new ones at the Optical layer, [presented an update](#).

Major Takeaways and Next Steps

1. Solidify Beta Testers. One of the goals of the workshop was to identify willing beta testers (beyond the 4 science drivers) who would work with FABRIC to ensure their experiments could be successfully run with the current software. While many experimenters are excited, FABRIC has to prioritize a subset, as working with experimenters in the early stages is time-consuming. Time frame: end of May.

2. Conduct User Acceptance Testing (UAT). Ensuring that the testbed contains usability features and is intuitive to everyone, including those without a long history of testbed use, is critical to success. The results of UAT will be used iteratively to improve any features the team didn't fully develop that are deemed critical. Time frame: end of August.

3. Increase the FABRIC User Base before Production. The attendees were mostly familiar with testbeds. As current or past users of large scale testbeds such as GENI or PAWR they understood the goal of the MVP and provided feedback about desired features they hoped to have seen on prior testbeds. However, there remains a gap between researchers who use testbeds to write papers about testbeds, and researchers in core areas such as Network Measurement, Security, AI, and CyberPhysical Systems that have not historically used testbeds. A similar gap remains between testbeds and CI operators, who have expressed a desire to test patches, configurations and systems in a non-production manner prior to deployment on campuses. While FABRIC is working closely with beta testers, this represents “friendly testers” who have long histories of testbeds as the crux of their work. Outreach to CISE communities that do not have a long history of testbed use is crucial. Time frame: ongoing until end of award.

4. Data Community Working Group. Data continues to be a challenge on several fronts. The workshop highlighted that experimenters are still unsure what data they need to *bring to FABRIC, want from FABRIC, and are willing to share* with other experimenters. While the FABRIC team is solidifying the storage schema and data classification schema, more conversations need to be held with experimenters. The team is constructing a survey about data needs and organizing a Data community working group, as discussed after the first workshop. We feel more equipped to conduct productive discussions on this topic, given the importance in the community on data sharing. Time frame: end of July.

5. Fall Workshop. Planning is beginning on the next FABRIC experimenter workshop, with a target of mid Fall.

Agenda

Day One - FABRIC Demonstrations & Feedback <i>April 8, 2021</i>		
<i>Time (ET)</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Presenter / Facilitator</i>
11:00 - 11:30	Social*	FABRIC Team
11:30 - 11:40	Welcome	Ilya Baldin, Deep Medhi, and Kevin Thompson
11:40 - 12:30	MVP Demo	Ilya Baldin & Paul Ruth
12:30 - 12:45	Break	
12:45 - 1:30	Measurement Framework Demo	Jim Griffioen & Yongwook Song
1:30 - 1:45	Not Your Cousin's Testbed	Phil Porras
1:45 - 2:45	Breakout Discussions Experiments in Research Domains:	Kuang-Ching Wang
	Networking	
	Measurement Researchers	
	Wireless Networking	
	Artificial Intelligence/ Machine Learning / Research Data	
	Security	
	Internet of Things	
	Federating Testbeds Owners/Conveners	
2:45 - 3:00	Break	
3:00 - 3:45	Large Group Discussion	Facilitator: Anita Nikolich
3:45 - 4:00	Review Day Two & Day One Closing	Ilya Baldin

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Day Two - Resource Gaps & Opportunities April 9, 2021

<i>Time (ET)</i>	<i>Topic</i>	<i>Presenter / Facilitator</i>
10:00 - 10:30	FAB Check-In	Anita Nikolich
10:30 - 11:00	CC* Check-In	Anita Nikolich
11:00 - 11:30	Social*	FABRIC Team
11:30 - 12:00	Open Mic	Kuang-Ching Wang
12:00 - 12:15	Next Generation Internet	Scott Shenker
12:15 - 12:45	Experimenters Spotlight	Russ Clark, Alex Afanasiev, Susmit Shannigrahi, and Alex Feltus
12:45 - 1:00	Student Spotlight	Kuang-Ching Wang, Mina William and Joe Biernacki
1:00 - 1:15	Break	
1:15 - 2:45	Experiments Whiteboard:	Facilitators: Ilya Baldin, Anita Nikolich, Jim Griffioen, Paul Ruth
	AI / ML / Research Data	
	Science CI	
	Edge	
	NDN	
2:45 - 3:00	Event Review and Next Steps	Ilya Baldin

*optional